

Effect of others' design evaluation on self design evaluation

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Abstract: I propose that consumers evaluate the design of a product based on how others evaluate its design. In particular, consumers tend to devalue the attributes others value highly. A pilot study and three experimental studies show that when others evaluate the design of a product based on its aesthetics, consumers tend to discount aesthetics in evaluating the design of a product. Conversely, when others evaluate the design of a product based on its function, function is discounted. Findings generally support that consumers' design evaluation is context-dependent. I discuss the implications of the present work to the research on design and marketing.

Key words: *design evaluation, need for uniqueness, aesthetics, function*

1. INTRODUCTION

Attempting to define design is a controversial task and there has been substantial discussion to reach a single, commonly agreed-upon notion of good design [1, 2]. Many design theorists and practitioners, however, generally agree that the design of a product can be judged by some combination of its aesthetic appeal and its functional appeal. For instance, theorists argue that aesthetics is visceral design and function is behavioral design [3].

Practitioners use aesthetics and functionality as two evaluation criteria for design award (e.g., Red Dot Design Award, International Forum Design Award, and Industrial Design Excellence Awards) [4].

Although design researchers believe that aesthetics and function contribute to design evaluation, marketing researchers tend to focus on aesthetics and shed little light on function [5]. In many prior marketing works, how to make a product aesthetically appealing [6, 7] and whether aesthetic appeal affects consumer behavior [8, 9] have been examined. The role of function in the context of product design, however, has been little discussed [10].

Therefore, the primary objective of the present work is to demonstrate that when evaluating the design of a product, consumers consider not only its aesthetics but also its function. Besides, I make two propositions in this article regarding how consumers make a design evaluation and consumption. Firstly, when evaluating the design of a product, consumers will assign weights on its aesthetics and its function differently depending on how others evaluate its design. This results in context-dependent design evaluation. This work, therefore, contributes to the marketing research on the effect of context on consumers' aesthetic evaluation [11, 12, 13] and consumers' choice [14, 15].

Secondly, I propose that consumers' design evaluation is not necessarily consistent with their consumption behavior, implying that good design does not always result in good business. Notice that this work does not raise the question of the commercial impact of product design [16, 17]. Instead, it offers a practical suggestion to designers on when they focus on aesthetics and when they consider function seriously.

The rest of this article is organized as follows. Firstly, I review design history and consumer behavior literature briefly to build a framework regarding how consumers make a design evaluation. Then, I report a pilot study and three main studies that test our hypothesis. Finally, I conclude with a discussion of the implications of this research for design and marketing.

2. DESIGN AS UNIQUENESS

Designers pursue uniqueness through aesthetics or function of their works. Thus, some design champions are considered institutional functionaries (e.g., Dieter Rams) and others artists (e.g., Philippe Starck). In post World War II when ornaments were used heavily to make product look better, a group of designers claimed a product should be stripped down to its fundamental features and necessary elements. For instance, Dieter Rams argued that a product should have few basic geometric shapes and non-fussy color combinations, suggesting less but better. Subsequently, function preceded aesthetics for everyday objects from chairs to kitchen utensils. However, others shed light on the aesthetics of a product to stand out from the crowds and move the design trend against minimalism. For instance, Philippe Starck developed citrus squeezer, Juicy Salif. This is an aesthetically appealing but practically limited in use. As briefly summarized, designers use either aesthetic appeal or functional appeal and achieve uniqueness, or good design.

Pursuing for uniqueness is not exclusive to professional designers. Marketing researchers have shown that consumers pursue unique products [19]. They try to construct a unique persona through the material objects they buy and display. Although some consumers buy unique products more often than others [20] and some product categories are more appropriate to pursue uniqueness than others [21], expressing uniqueness via consumption behavior is generally a safe way to achieve a different sense of being without damaging an individual's sense of social assimilation [22]. Therefore, consumers tend not to choose a product when others prefer the same one, in particular when it is a symbolic product [21].

My guiding premise is that consumers' design evaluation does not differ from professional designers' design evaluation; they both will equate good design with uniqueness. Therefore, when consumers evaluate how well a product is designed, they consider how distinctive the product is from other products. This leads to an interesting hypothesis that consumers' design evaluation depends on others' design evaluation. Suppose that you evaluate the design of two laptop messenger bags, and one is aesthetically appealing (e.g., stylistic strap and good material) whereas the other is functional (e.g., a padded compartment and several pockets). You may consider both their aesthetics and function when evaluating how well the two bags are designed. However, you may evaluate the relative superiority of their goodness of design differently depending on which option is unique. For instance, when others (e.g., friends) consider aesthetics more heavily than function, an aesthetic option is less unique than a functional option, which in turn leads you to decrease the design evaluation of the aesthetically appealing bag. Conversely, when function dominates aesthetics (e.g., business clients), consumers will decrease the weight of the functional impact on design, discounting the design evaluation of the functionally appealing bag. This suggests that others' design evaluation shapes one's design evaluation through the degree to which a product is unique. More formally speaking,

Hypothesis 1: When evaluating the design of a product, consumers consider function more heavily than aesthetics when others consider aesthetics more heavily than function.

Hypothesis 2: When evaluating the design of a product, consumers consider aesthetics more heavily than function when others consider function more heavily than aesthetics.

3. PILOT STUDY

Objective, design, and procedure

A pilot study was conducted to test if consumers base their design evaluation on aesthetics and function. In total, 90 undergraduate students were recruited from the participant pool at the Rotman School of Management, University of Toronto. A single open-ended question was administered; “what do you consider when you judge the design of a product (i.e., how well a product is designed)?”

Subjects produced a total of 302 responses or an average of 3.39 responses per subject. Two judges, the author and a graduate student who is blind to the research project, categorized them independently (inter-judge agreement = 83 percent). Unfortunately, inter-judge agreement score was not high enough to use the data as it was. Therefore, I hired two experts, professional designers, and went through multiple times of discussions to resolve any discrepancy between two judges. In this case, two professional designers earned their master degrees and one works at a graphic design studio in Toronto and the other works at an design consulting firm in China.

Findings and discussion

Three findings are obtained. Firstly, as expected, majority of subjects indicated that they use either aesthetic appeal or functional appeal when evaluating the design of a product. About 68% of the responses belong to either an aesthetic appeal or a functional appeal. Out of 302 responses, 93 responses (31%) are categorized as an aesthetic appeal (e.g., sleek, eye-catching, attractive, aesthetically pleasing, looking good, stylish, and colorful) and 113 responses (37%) are categorized as a functional appeal (e.g., function, features, efficient, effective, practical, useful, and convenient). The responses that are not categorized as either an aesthetic appeal or a functional appeal include, for instance, weight (9%), technological advancement (4%), differentiation (3%), simplicity (3%), and modernity (2%), to name a few. Secondly, many subjects use conflicting criteria for their design evaluation, implying that they do not reach a clear consensus about good design. For instance, technological advancement is often accomplished when simplicity is sacrificed. Classic products are not modern. Finally and most importantly to the present work, more than half of the subjects (59%) responded both an aesthetic appeal and a functional appeal for their design evaluation. Only 16 subjects answered an aesthetic appeal only and the other 16 answered a functional appeal only.

In sum, findings provide evidence that consumers use aesthetics and function for their design evaluation. Further, they showed that subjects had an unclear understanding about design, implying that when asked to evaluate the design of a product, consumers may construct design evaluation instantly by placing weights on evaluation criteria.

4. STUDY 1: INNOVATIVE PORTABLE DEVICE

Objective, design, and procedure

The objective of study 1 was to test hypothesis 1 and 2; whether others' design evaluation affects self design evaluation. It employed a 2 (context: school vs. business) between-subjects design and 52 undergraduate students participated in the study recruited from the participant pool at the Rotman School of Management, University of

Toronto. Subjects read a brief description about a hypothetical innovative portable device; it sends and receives emails and finds places for users. Then, the half of the subjects read they would use the product at school (“you can exchange emails with your friends and find places to have fun with them”) and the other half read they would use the product for business (“you can exchange emails with your business clients and find places to have meetings with them”). Next, two competing options about the product were described; one is sleek and eye-catching (aesthetic option) and the other is easy to use and has many features (functional option). Finally, subjects were asked to make a design evaluation (choice of an option that is better designed) and a purchase decision (choice of an option that is more likely to purchase). Afterwards, they were thanked and debriefed.

Findings

Context influenced subjects’ design evaluation but did not influence their purchase decision. When subjects were instructed that they would use the product at school, fewer subjects (33%) indicated that the aesthetic option is better designed than the functional option (67%). However, when they were told that the product would be used for business, more indicated the aesthetic option as a better designed option (aesthetic = 60% vs. functional = 40%), showing that context influenced consumers’ design evaluation ($X^2(1) = 3.71, p = .05$).

Figure 1. DESIGN EVALUATION AS A FUNCTION OF CONTEXT (Study 1)

Purchase decision did not differ depending on context. Subjects chose the functional option for their purchase decision regardless of whether using it at school (functional = 78% vs. aesthetic = 22%) or for business (functional = 76% vs. aesthetic = 24%, $X^2(1) = 0.02, p > .10$).

Discussion

The finding supports that context affects consumers’ design evaluation; when consumers infer that others may consider aesthetics heavily (e.g., at school), they discount aesthetics for their design evaluation. Conversely, when others consider function (e.g., for business), they discount function for their design evaluation. This implies that uniqueness dictates consumers’ design evaluation. An interesting finding is that context did not affect consumers’ purchase decision, suggesting that consumers’ design evaluation is not necessarily consistent

with their consumption.

This study, however, has two major limitations. Firstly, two options were verbally described. Although aesthetics and function were carefully manipulated through the two most frequently identified responses from the pilot study, individual subjects might have interpreted verbal descriptions differently because of ambiguity. Secondly, the discrepancies between design evaluation and purchase decision were found from the aesthetic option only and not from the functional option. This leads to an alternative hypothesis that consumers' design evaluation is not driven by both the aesthetic aspect and the functional aspect of a product but merely by the aesthetic aspect of a product. Two limitations were addressed in study 2.

5. STUDY 2: LAPTOP MESSENGER BAG

Objective, design, and procedure

Study 2 aimed to replicate the finding in study 1 and addresses two limitations. In this study, the visual as well as the verbal description about two options were provided to eliminate any ambiguity of verbal description, and the aesthetic option became more attractive than the functional option intentionally to see if consumers' design evaluation was influenced by not merely the aesthetics of a product but both the aesthetics and the function of a product.

Study design and procedure is identical with study 1 except stimuli, laptop messenger bag. It employed a 2 (context: school vs. business) between-subjects design and 44 undergraduate students participated in the study. The aesthetic option ("Bag B") had higher value on aesthetic attributes (e.g., stripe and exterior texture) and the functional option ("Bag A") had better functional features (e.g., a laptop compartment and pockets). In this study, subjects made a design evaluation and a purchase decision between two options, and then answered two manipulation check questions; one was about aesthetic appeal ("which bag is more aesthetically appealing in general?") and the other was about functional appeal ("which bag is more functional in general?"). Then, subjects were thanked and debriefed.

Figure 2. A FUNCTIONAL OPTION (Bag A) AND AN AESTHETIC OPTION (Bag B)

Findings

Firstly, aesthetic appeal and functional appeal were manipulated successfully. Majority of the subjects (91%) indicated that Bag B was aesthetically more appealing than Bag A. Besides, majority of subjects (98%) answered that Bag A was functionally more appealing than Bag B. Two scores showed no difference in terms of context (aesthetic appeal: $X^2(1) = 0.59, p > .10$, functional appeal: $X^2(1) = 0.78, p > .10$).

As expected, context influenced subjects' design evaluation but did not influence their purchase decision. When instructed that the bag is used at school, fewer subjects indicated that the aesthetic option (36%) is designed better than the functional option (64%). When instructed that the bag is used for business, more chose the aesthetic option as a better designed option (aesthetic = 63% vs. functional = 37%), showing that context influenced consumers' design evaluation ($X^2(1) = 3.20, p < .10$).

Figure 3. DESIGN EVALUATION AS A FUNCTION OF CONTEXT (Study 2)

Purchase decision was not influenced by context but differently from study 1. Subjects chose the aesthetic option for their purchase decision regardless of whether it was used at school (aesthetic = 64% vs. functional = 36%) or for business (aesthetic = 74% vs. functional = 26%, $X^2(1) = 0.47, p > .10$).

Discussion

Study 2 replicated the findings obtained from the prior study; context leads consumers to make a different design evaluation about the identical product but it does not influence their purchase decision, resulting in the discrepancies between design evaluation and consumption. It also addressed limitations of study 1 by demonstrating that context influences design evaluation not merely through aesthetics but through (the uniqueness of) both aesthetics and function.

Two prior studies showed that when context changed, consumers' design evaluation changed. None of the prior studies, however, directly manipulated uniqueness and tested its impact on consumers' design evaluation. Although it is fair to assume that people may weigh different aspects of a product in different contexts, it is not clear whether consumers actually infer students weigh aesthetics more heavily than function and business people weigh function more heavily than aesthetics. This limitation was addressed in the next study.

6. STUDY 3: COMPUTER KEYBOARD

Objective, design, and procedure

Study 3 used two options of a computer keyboard for its stimuli; an aesthetic option had a better outlook and a functional option had more features (e.g., characters are illuminated and three levels of back lights are provided). Different than prior studies, this study manipulated not only context but also the popularity of the two options in order to test the effect of uniqueness on consumers' design evaluation. Therefore, it employed a 2 (context: school vs. business) x 2 (popularity: an aesthetic (functional) option is popular among students (business people) vs. an aesthetic (functional) option is popular among business people (students)) between-subjects design and in total, 62 undergraduate students participated in the study. Context was manipulated in the same as in prior studies; subjects were instructed that they would use a computer keyboard either at school or for business. Popularity was manipulated by a paragraph of information about which keyboard option is popular among whom. In one condition, they were instructed that the aesthetic option was popular among students and the functional option was popular among business people. This condition is consistent with the assumption applied to the prior studies. In the other condition, the popularity of the two options was reversed; the aesthetic option was popular among business people and the functional option was popular among students. Then, subjects indicated their design evaluation and purchase decision and then answered two manipulation check questions. They were thanked and debriefed afterwards.

Findings

Firstly, aesthetic appeal and functional appeal were manipulated successfully. Majority of the subjects (73%) indicated that the aesthetic option was aesthetically more appealing than the functional option, and majority of subjects (85%) answered that the functional option was functionally more appealing than the aesthetic option.

Two scores showed no effect of context or popularity, demonstrating that the two options were successfully manipulated regardless of two manipulations.

As expected, consumers' design evaluation is determined by both context and popularity. When the aesthetic option was popular among students and the functional option was popular among business people, consumers' design evaluation was consistent with the findings obtained from the prior studies; fewer subjects (47%) indicated that the aesthetic option was better designed than the functional option (53%) when the computer keyboard was used at school, whereas more chose the aesthetic option as a better designed when the computer keyboard was used for business (aesthetic = 94% vs. functional = 6%), showing that context influenced design evaluation ($X^2(1) = 8.33, p < .01$). Design evaluation scores, however, were reversed when each option was popular among different groups of people; the aesthetic option was popular among business people and the functional option was popular among students. In this popularity condition, more subjects chose the aesthetic option as a better designed option when using it at school (aesthetic = 87% vs. functional = 13%) and fewer subjects chose the same option as a better designed option when using it for business (aesthetic = 44% vs. functional = 54%), demonstrating that popularity affected design evaluation ($X^2(1) = 6.23, p < .05$).

Figure 4. DESIGN EVALUATION AS A FUNCTION OF CONTEXT AND POPULARITY (Study 3)

As shown in previous studies, neither context nor popularity influenced purchase decision. Subjects did not choose one option significantly more than the other option for their purchase decision regardless of whether the aesthetic option is popular among students (aesthetic = 42% vs. functional = 58%, $X^2(1) = 0.27, p > .10$) or among business people (aesthetic = 29% vs. functional = 71%, $X^2(1) = 1.69, p > .10$).

Discussion

Study 3 provides evidence that consumers' design evaluation is not merely shaped by context but is determined by how consumers infer what others consider in each context. When subjects were informed that the aesthetic (functional) option was popular among students (business people), this study replicated the findings from the prior studies. However, when the popularity of product options differed from the assumption of the prior studies, the opposite pattern of design evaluation was found. I added another piece of evidence that consumers' design evaluation is not consistent with their purchase decision.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The present work offers a piece of clue regarding what is a good design for consumers. One pilot study and the three studies account for how consumers place weight on rather conflicting criteria—aesthetics and function; they discount aesthetics when others consider aesthetics heavily and discount function when others consider function heavily, implying that consumers' design evaluation is context dependent and, more importantly, depends on how unique a product is.

Interestingly, consumers' purchase decision was not influenced by either context (study 1 and 2) or popularity (study 3). Therefore, some options were evaluated highly in terms of design but were not chosen for consumption. Then, why did subjects sometimes avoid buying a better designed product? I suspect that consumers' design evaluation requires significantly less degree of justification compared to their purchase decision [24]. Indeed, the term, design, is often considered as an expression of personal taste in our daily life, but purchase decision needs to be made effortfully. According to this view, consumers' design evaluation may not indicate their consumption behavior but simply satisfies their need for uniqueness. More research is called for what drive the discrepancies between design and business and when or how they can be mitigated.

This work not only contributes to the marketing research on product design but also to the decision making research on hedonic-utilitarian choice. If people are allowed to express their need for uniqueness, the effects reported in the prior decision making works are reversed [11, 12, 17, 23]. For instance, if others choose a utilitarian rather than hedonic option but people want to be unique, they may choose a hedonic option, differently from the findings suggested by the prior works.

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